

Mobilization of Iron in Soil and Its Influence on Phosphate Availability Through the Chelating Effects of Aqueous Extracts of Some Green Manuring Plant Materials

DHRUBAJYOTI BHATTACHARYA and BISWANATH DAS

Department of Soil Science and Agricultural Chemistry, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Kalyani, West Bengal

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Mobilization of iron in soil through the chelation effects of the aqueous extracts of Alfalfa, Berseem and *P. calcaratus* plant materials, and its effect on the release of phosphate has been studied with two types of West Bengal soil at different levels of pH and different submergence periods. The maximal release of iron was observed in all cases on incubation of the soil samples for 15 days. Irrespective of soils the order of chelating ability was observed to be Alfalfa > *P. calcaratus* > Berseem. No definite correlation could, however, be obtained between the release of iron and phosphate availability.

THE role of soil organic matter in pedogenesis and soil fertility was brought into focus due to studies of Kononova¹, Bloomfield^{2,3,4} and many other soil scientists. Transport of metal ions, namely iron, due to chelation by certain groups of chelating agents, present in degraded soil organic matter, has been studied by many investigators⁵⁻⁸. Studies reveal that presence of natural chelating agents is one of the several plausible explanations of how plants are able to obtain elements like iron which is ordinarily very much insoluble. The use of synthetic chelates for adequate supply of micronutrients to the deficient plants is a recent trend.

Enrichment of soils with nitrogen by supplying green manure prior to cultivation is widely accepted. Our knowledge about the added organic matter through green manuring is still scanty. It is presumed that apart from its capability to enhance the nitrogen percentage, the organic matter thus added through green manuring must have some other influences on soil fertility.

In an earlier communication⁹, we have discussed the phenomena of iron mobilisation and phosphate availability in two major types of West Bengal soil through the chelation behaviour of some compounds which contain the functional groups generally involved in the chelation process in soil. In this paper we have studied the behaviour of three green manuring plant extracts on the same soils in respect of iron mobilization and phosphate availability.

Materials and Methods

Soils: Two types of soil, one typical alluvial soil from Nadia district (C-soil) and one red soil of Purulia (R-soil), have been used in this investigation. The soil nature, their physical and chemical charac-

teristics were already reported in our previous paper⁹.

Green-Manuring Plant Materials: Three different leguminous plants, widely used as green manure, were selected for the experiment. They are Alfalfa (*Medicago sativa*), Berseem (*Trifolium alexandrinum*) and *Phaseolus calcaratus*.

Preparation of Plant Extracts: The chopped plant materials (stem and leaves) were thoroughly washed with distilled water, dried in sun, milled and subsequently passed through 40-mesh sieve. A 25 g portion of the plant dust was taken in 240 ml of distilled water and was shaken intermittently for five days, so that total shaking period was 24 hr. The slurry was then filtered through Whatman No. 1 filter paper under reduced pressure and the final volume of the filtrate was made upto 250 ml with 2 to 3 washings of the residue so that each 10 ml portion of the extract would represent 1 g of dried plant material. These were examined for the contents of iron and phosphorus, and the data is depicted in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS OF THE PLANT EXTRACTS FOR IRON AND PHOSPHORUS

No. of Experiment	Name of the Plant	Content of Iron in mg/10 g of dry dust	Content of Phosphorus in mg/10 g of dry dust
1.	<i>Phaseolus calcaratus</i>	0.72	4.42
2.	Alfalfa	0.62	3.51
3.	Berseem	0.51	3.92

The characteristics of both the soils and standard methods used in this investigation are same as those already reported in our previous communication⁹.

Experimental

To 10 g of soil 5 ml of *N* acetic acid along with 15 ml of the plant extract were added and the final volume was made upto 50 ml with distilled water in specimen tubes. The initial incubation *pH* (from 3 to 9) was adjusted with fractional *pH* papers, by adding 2(*N*) NaOH or 1(*N*) HCl as required. The batch of tubes were preserved in dark to avoid any photochemical decomposition and was taken out after specific time intervals, namely 7, 15 and 21 days to study the release of iron and phosphate as a function of time.

After the due period of incubation the suspensions were filtered through Whatman No. 42 filter paper under reduced pressure. No washing was done. The equilibrium *pH* values of the filtrates were then recorded with a *pH* meter. The solutions were then oxidised at hot condition with the mixture of concentrated H₂SO₄ and HNO₃ to break the chelated complex and to decompose the organic matter. The residual liquids were then transferred into 50 ml volumetric flasks and water was added upto the marks. Iron and phosphorus were estimated colorimetrically by taking appropriate aliquots from the above stocks. The results are shown in Tables 2, 3 and 4.

In order to assess the effect of submergence alone, the soils were incubated at the different experimental *pH* under same volume of distilled water. In absence of any treatment, in both soils soluble iron content was progressively decreased on increasing the *pH* and incubating for a maximum period of 15 days. Amount of soluble phosphorus was found to be maximal (0.19 mg/100 g) at *pH* 5.7 for the C-soil; whereas, for the R-soil the maximal value (0.14 mg/100 g) was obtained at *pH* around 7.0.

Results and Discussion

From Table 2, *P. calcaratus* extract is found to transport iron in appreciably higher quantity at *pH* 8.0 in both the soils after 7 days of incubation. This is comparable to the behaviour of polycarboxylic acid⁹. The sharp fall after this maxima manifests the instability of iron-acid complex or possibly stands as a limiting *pH* for these anions to keep the complex in a state of dispersion or solution.

After 15 days a marked rise in quantity of released iron from *pH* 3 to 8, especially in the case of R-soil, clearly demonstrates that all the possible components in the plant extracts, e.g., polyphenols, organic acids and amino acids are at their highest level of activity. The rise in iron concentration after *pH* 8.40 is possibly due to the activity of amino acids present in the extract, as supported by the study on iron release with the pure compound glutamic acid⁹.

The initial higher availability is the distinctive feature of C-soil which is possibly due to more labile

nature of iron compounds present in this type of alluvial soils.

On incubation for 21 days a general trend of decrease in iron concentration was noticed in acidic region in case of both the soils, possibly due to atmospheric oxidation: surface adsorption on ferric oxide micelle thus formed, or due to possible microbial activity, inherent in unsterilised soils, which becomes significant in that *pH* range.

The effect of Berseem extract on iron mobilization can be observed in Table 3. Two distinct zones of *pH*, one from 3.0 to 4.5 and other from 7.5 to 8.5, where significant release of iron took place are quite evident from the table. The acidic range is due to the activity of the weaker chelating agents, i.e., amino acids and polyphenols and higher *pH* range is due to the polycarboxylic acids as found in the case of pure compounds⁹.

On 21 days of incubation a general trend of decrease, irrespective of the *pH*, is observed. The possible reason of this has already been discussed earlier. Here also a general saturation effect was noticed at the 15 day-stage demonstrating the highest level of activity of all chelating agents.

The higher release of iron by Alfalfa extract is its distinctive feature, as shown in Table 4. In both the soils no maxima, excepting at *pH* 8.0, has been obtained. This shows an overwhelming effect of the acidic fraction on the other components. However, the saturation phenomena observed after 15 and 21 days, as apparent from the plateau region, are in favour of the existence of the weaker ligands and their chelating effect at lower *pH*. The plateau indicates that *pH* has no appreciable effect on mobilization of iron with alfalfa extract on prolonged submergence.

The presence of maxima around *pH* 8.0 is case of all the three extracts are in favour of the presence of polycarboxylic acids in appreciable quantity in all the three plants which may cause higher iron availability in soil at a higher *pH*. Mobilization of iron at lower *pH* range by *P. calcaratus* extract shows the high content of amino acids and polyphenols in this plant, and greater mobilization at higher *pH* by alfalfa extract indicates high content of acidic fraction in this plant.

From Table 2, it is obvious that *P. calcaratus* extract steadily increases the phosphate availability upto 15 days of incubation, in both the soils under investigation. In both the soils a general trend of decrease is observed around *pH* 8.0. The increase in phosphate concentration at higher *pH* seems to be due to anion exchange with OH⁻ ion or due to chelation of calcium which is beyond the scope of our present study. Excepting certain points, a correlation between release of iron and availability of phosphate could not be established.

From the Table 3, it is found that effect of Berseem extract also follows the same trend as in the case of *P. calcaratus*. The fall in phosphate availability around *pH* 8.0 is, however, not so pronounced. This

TABLE 2—MOBILIZATION OF IRON AND PHOSPHORUS WITH *P. calcaratus* EXTRACT

Soil	After 7 days			After 15 days			After 21 days		
	pH	Fe mg/ 100 g	P mg/ 100 g	pH	Fe mg/ 100 g	P mg/ 100 g	pH	Fe mg/ 100 g	P mg/ 100 g
C-Soil	3.30	1.66	0.91	2.60	1.83	1.13	3.50	1.74	0.91
	4.20	1.83	0.99	4.60	1.74	1.24	4.20	1.74	0.65
	5.00	1.74	0.91	5.30	1.78	1.01	4.80	1.74	0.64
	6.50	1.58	1.01	6.80	1.66	1.24	7.10	1.66	0.66
	8.20	1.74	1.18	7.80	1.74	0.91	7.50	1.74	0.96
	8.80	0.58	1.21	9.20	0.68	1.01	8.70	1.42	0.68
R-Soil	3.75	0.91	1.08	3.40	1.66	0.91	3.70	1.62	0.91
	4.15	0.83	0.91	4.90	1.66	0.95	4.10	0.91	0.91
	5.00	0.83	0.91	6.50	1.74	0.79	5.20	0.58	0.64
	8.00	1.74	0.43	8.00	1.83	0.75	7.90	1.66	0.48
	8.20	1.16	0.63	8.40	1.24	0.63	8.40	1.66	0.58
	8.90	0.75	0.58	9.50	1.56	1.01	9.00	1.60	0.80

TABLE 3—MOBILIZATION OF IRON AND PHOSPHORUS WITH BERSEEM EXTRACT

Soil	After 7 days			After 15 days			After 21 days		
	pH	Fe mg/ 100 g	P mg/ 100 g	pH	Fe mg/ 100 g	P mg/ 100 mg	pH	Fe mg/ 100 g	P mg/ 100 g
C-Soil	3.25	1.51	0.85	3.10	1.62	1.08	3.20	1.74	1.08
	4.40	1.51	1.08	3.60	3.60	1.47	4.00	1.49	1.11
	6.50	0.83	1.11	5.80	1.34	1.16	6.30	0.74	0.86
	7.50	1.08	1.11	8.30	1.62	1.16	7.60	1.23	1.03
	8.30	1.33	1.01	7.80	1.62	1.11	8.50	0.91	1.18
	9.00	0.83	1.11	8.80	0.91	1.29	9.40	0.91	1.18
R-Soil	3.05	0.89	0.88	3.60	0.90	0.59	3.20	1.34	0.79
	4.10	1.08	0.91	4.10	0.62	0.56	4.40	0.89	0.85
	5.60	0.91	0.85	5.20	0.62	0.53	5.90	0.64	0.53
	7.45	1.33	0.48	7.50	1.67	0.76	7.60	1.58	0.75
	8.20	0.91	0.64	8.10	1.24	0.65	8.30	1.08	0.65
	8.40	0.69	0.91	8.60	1.24	0.85	9.30	0.71	1.01

TABLE 4—MOBILIZATION OF IRON AND PHOSPHORUS WITH *Alfalfa* EXTRACT

Soil	After 7 days			After 15 days			After 21 days		
	pH	Fe mg/ 100 g	P mg/ 100 g	pH	Fe mg/ 100 g	P mg/ 100 g	pH	Fe mg/ 100 g	P mg/ 100 g
C-Soil	2.50	1.78	1.08	2.80	2.14	1.83	3.30	1.78	1.18
	3.60	1.49	1.18	3.70	1.58	1.68	5.50	1.53	1.08
	6.90	1.12	1.11	7.00	1.98	1.54	6.30	1.49	1.18
	7.70	1.74	1.11	7.50	2.21	2.01	7.70	1.74	1.25
	8.00	1.74	0.96	8.10	2.21	0.98	8.20	1.62	1.18
	9.00	1.42	1.10	8.70	1.58	1.02	9.90	1.42	1.18
R-Soil	2.70	1.16	1.08	3.00	1.58	1.25	4.00	1.55	0.66
	3.40	0.996	0.91	3.90	1.35	1.00	4.80	1.49	0.79
	5.80	0.80	0.64	6.00	1.98	0.60	6.50	1.58	0.963
	6.60	1.74	0.47	7.50	2.14	0.66	7.60	1.66	1.11
	7.80	1.25	0.58	7.80	1.98	0.66	8.40	1.42	1.11
	8.00	1.25	0.68	8.50	1.25	0.67	9.00	1.49	1.11

is probably due to higher stabilities of the chelated complexes so formed with organic constituents present in this plant material. In C-soil, a marked fall in available phosphate at pH 6.3 after 21 days of incubation bears a distinct relation with fall in concentration of iron at that point. For R-soil most of the points corresponding to the maximal and minimal contents of available phosphate are found to bear a relation with those of iron mobilization. Higher availability of phosphate beyond pH

8.0 may not be due to mobilization of iron bound phosphate alone but due to some other phenomena as explained earlier.

The effect of Alfalfa extract on C-soil as found in Table 4 shows some unusual trend. After 15 days of submergence, phosphate availability maxima at pH 7.5 can be highly correlated with that of iron-release at that pH, but after that sharp peak, available phosphate content falls abruptly near its half value which is not totally understood. As observed in case of iron-release, after longer period of incubation, pH of the media has no marked effect on the release of phosphate with Alfalfa extract. Its behaviour with R-soil is quite peculiar. Higher release of phosphate at low pH after 7 and 15 days of incubation and at higher pH after 21 days of incubation must be due to some other factors associated with the properties of the plant extract or the soil itself.

The compatibility of Alfalfa as green manure over Berseem and *P. calcaratus*, in its iron mobilizing power as well as in releasing phosphate is quite clear. For Alfalfa chelation continues upto 15 days. Berseem also follows the same trend, but its mobilizing power is least among the three plants studied. On using *P. calcaratus*, extract chelation is completed within 7 days. It is also indicated that the

chelated complex formed in the latter case is much more resistant to further immobilization than those formed in the case of other two.

In order to see the effect of submergence without addition of any organic matter further experiments were conducted. The results of 15 days of submergence indicate in general an aerobic reduction of ferric phosphates with resultant increase in phosphate availability. The relative amounts of iron and phosphate released, however, clearly signify the importance of green manuring crops to enhance their mobilization in both types of soil studied herewith.

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